

National Leprosy Conference 2025

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Abstract Book

Ministry of Health

Anti-Leprosy Campaign

World Health Organization
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LEPROSY
INITIATIVE

PP-6: Effectiveness of a holistic approach in leprosy control- Integration of monitoring of leprosy control activities within epidemiological reviews in Regional Directorate of Health services Colombo

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Background

Surveillance and control activities are implemented for many communicable disease conditions at the district level. These activities are technically mentored at national level through vertical programs by multiple stakeholders. Integration of relevant possible domains within the mandate of “epidemiological reviews” would potentially prevent duplication of efforts at the ground level.

Description of the initiative

The district team with the collaboration of the provincial team had three consultative sessions with all relevant staff member categories at 18 Medical Officer of Health areas within the Colombo Regional Directorate of Health Services (RDHS- Colombo). Expert inputs were also obtained from the national level stakeholders. Ways of integration of communicable disease control monitoring including that of leprosy, was identified. These included inclusion of leprosy data fields to the; Weekly Epidemiological Review Format, the “Progress monitoring boards printed at the MOH offices”, progress monitoring powerpoint slides of weekly district level reviews, monthly Heads of Institution (HoI) meetings and to assessment formats of annual appraisal program of RDHS-Colombo

Methods used for the evaluation

A combination of quantitative and qualitative methods are used. These included; coverage and timeliness indicators utilizing at above activities, qualitative observations at field-level observations like team supervisions.

Results

This integration approach has yielded measurable improvements in leprosy surveillance, particularly in contact screening activities. The weekly reviews are happening at all MOH areas and continuous feedback reports are reported by the district team. The supervision boards are updated in all MOH areas. The presentations done at HoI meetings and weekly district level reviews include leprosy-related indicators.

Lessons Learnt

Integrating monitoring of leprosy surveillance and control within broader public health indicators promotes a more holistic and efficient approach to disease control. Linking this monitoring with routine review processes ensures the sustainability